

Coding Techniques under Study at NASA

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Abstract—NASA is studying coding techniques in an effort to achieve communications from spacecraft at lower effective isotropic radiated power. Presently NASA's coding standards support a (2,1,6) convolutional inner code and a Reed-Solomon (255,223,8) outer code; during the past two years studies were conducted on the performance of a long constraint length (2,1,14) convolutional code and the Turbo codes. Flight experiments will lead to results on the actual performance, complexity and implementation of such coding systems.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Future trends in space communications will require NASA to support higher data rate scientific imaging instruments operating on smaller spacecraft at reduced power levels. In an effort to accommodate these future trends, NASA is investigating channel coding techniques that will enable the scientific satellites to communicate at a lower Effective Isotropic Radiated Power (EIRP). The channel coding techniques presented are of two types, convolutional and block codes, which can lower the EIRP for telemetry applications.

2. PRESENT TELEMETRY CODES

Figure 1 depicts a communications channel with both transmitter and receiver.

Figure 1. The Three Main Parts of the Communications System

For telemetry, NASA prefers the use of a concatenated code, which is the concatenation of two dissimilar codes, such as a convolutional code followed by a block code. The inner code is a non-systematic, rate 1/2, constraint length 7 convolutional code (2,1,6), and the outer code is rate 223/255 8-bit/byte Reed-Solomon (R-S) (255,223,8) code.

Convolutional Codes

NASA currently uses a transparent convolutional code which is well suited for channels with predominantly Gaussian noise. The convolutional decoder uses a maximum-likelihood (Viterbi) Decoder (VD) algorithm. If the decoder's correction capability is exceeded, undetected burst errors may appear in the output. The convolutional code may be used alone, as described in this section, or in conjunction with an R-S code described in the following sections. The convolutional code has the following characteristics.

- 1) Nomenclature: Convolutional code with maximum-likelihood (Viterbi) decoding
- 2) Code rate: 1/2 bit per symbol
- 3) Constraint length: 7 bits
- 4) Connection vectors:
 $G1 = 1111001$
 $G2 = 1011011$
- 5) Phase relationship: G1 is associated with the first symbol
- 6) Symbol inversion: On the output path of G2

An encoder block diagram is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Convolutional Encoder Block Diagram

The results shown in this section were obtained by using soft bit decisions with three-bit quantization as inputs to the Viterbi decoder.

Reed-Solomon Codes

The R-S code defined in this section is a powerful burst error correcting code. In addition, this code has an extremely low undetected error rate; i.e., the decoder can reliably indicate whether it can make the proper corrections or not. To achieve this reliability, proper codeblock synchronization is mandatory.

The R-S code may be used alone, and as such it provides an excellent forward error correction capability in a Gaussian or burst-noise channel. However, should the R-S code alone not provide sufficient coding gain, it may be concatenated with the convolutional

code. In a concatenated code, the R-S code is the outer code, while the convolutional code is the inner code.

The parameters of the R-S code are as follows:

- 1) $J = 8$ bits per R-S symbol.
- 2) $E = 16$ symbol error correction capability within an R-S codeword.
- 3) $n = 2^J - 1$ symbols per R-S codeword.
- 4) $k = n - 2E$ information symbols per R-S codeword.
- 5) Field generator polynomial:
 $F(x) = x^8 + x^7 + x^2 + x + 1$
 over $GF(2)$.

Figure 3 depicts the performance of the above codes in a Gaussian noise channel.

Figure 3. Relative Performance of Concatenated Coding with R-S Outer Code (R-S Ideal Interleaving and No-Interleaving Comparison)

It should be noted that in the case of R-S codes, standalone or concatenated, the probability of undetected error is much smaller than the probability of error because over 98% of errors are detectable. Figure 4 shows the performance of some inner codes

relative to code efficiency for a Bit Error Rate (BER) of 10^{-5} .

Figure 4. Approaching Capacity with Complex Convolutional Codes

3. TELEMETRY CODES UNDER CONSIDERATION

In the past few years a number of coding schemes have been proposed for achieving near capacity performance in the power-limited region of the Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) channel, such as multilevel codes, cascaded convolutional codes, product codes with convolutional codes, and convolutional codes with sequential decoding. The performance of some of these codes is shown in Figure 4.

The Big Viterbi Convolutional Code

One of the codes under consideration is the Big Viterbi Decoder (BVD) convolutional (2,1,14) code. The BVD is a non-systematic transparent code with the following characteristics:

- 1) Nomenclature: Convolutional code with maximum-likelihood (Viterbi) decoding
- 2) Code rate: 1/2 Bit Per Symbol
- 3) Constraint length: 15 Bits

4) Connection vectors:

$$G1 = 101110111010001$$

$$G2 = 110001111001011$$

5) Phase relationship: G1 is associated with the first symbol

6) Symbol inversion: On the output path of G2

The Performance of this code compared to that of the (2,1,6) VD is shown in Figure 5. Note that at a BER of 10^{-5} the BVD offers a 1.7 dB improvement but also higher complexity.

Figure 5. The Performance of the (2,1,14) BVD Compared to the (2,1,6) VD

Turbo Codes

Turbo codes were invented by Claude Berrou and others in 1993 [1]. Their performance comes closest to the channel capacity, as will be shown in the following paragraphs.

Turbo codes, which are block codes, are a parallel concatenation of convolutional encoders combined with iterative Maximum A Posteriori (MAP) decoding to achieve a BER of 10^{-5} with a Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) of only 0.7 dB.

Turbo codes are only 0.7 dB away from the channel capacity. The channel capacity, for a rate 1/2 code with Binary Phase Shift Keying (BPSK) modulation on the AWGN channel is 0 dB. See Figure 4.

The following is a brief description of this coding system, followed by the performance results.

Turbo Encoder

As shown in Figure 6 the Turbo code uses two identical rate $R = 1/2$, $v = 4$, convolutional encoders in systematic-feedback form in a "parallel concatenation" configuration.

Figure 6. Block Diagram of the Turbo Encoder

Each encoder is punctured to rate $R = 2/3$. The systematic form of the encoders results in each information bit being sent only once. Thus, the overall rate of the Turbo encoder is 1/2.

The pseudorandom interleaver ensures, with high probability, that the codeword generated by the first encoder in response to the input is different from the codeword generated by the second encoder in response to the same input after interleaving; in particular, it decorrelates the outputs of the two encoders and causes two codewords of different weight to be selected by each encoder for the same input sequence.

Turbo Decoder

For the Turbo decoder of Figure 7 the parallel concatenation of encoders is iteratively decoded by two identical MAP decoders.

Figure 7: Block Diagram of the Turbo Decoder

In order for the iterative decoding technique to be effective, soft information must be passed from one decoder to the next. This is done using the MAP estimates, $\Lambda(k)$, from the MAP decoding algorithm. Each pass through the two decoders counts as one iteration. A total of 18 iterations are required to achieve a BER of 10^{-5} with SNR of 0.7dB. The effect of the number of iterations is discussed below.

Turbo Code Performance

The parameters that control the Turbo code performance are the length of the pseudorandom interleaver and the number of iterations in the decoder.

The original Turbo code with an $N = 65536$ pseudorandom interleaver was found to have $d_{\text{free}} = 6$, $N_{\text{free}} = 3$, and $w_{\text{free}} = 6$.

The free-distance asymptote for the Turbo code is then

$$\frac{3}{65536} \left(\frac{6}{2}\right) \text{erfc} \left(\sqrt{\frac{0.5E_b}{N_o}}\right)$$

Figure 8 shows that the performance of the Turbo code is distinctly different from the performance of the Maximal Free Distance (MFD) (2,1,14) code with Viterbi decoding.

Figure 8. Asymptotic Performance of the Turbo Code Compared to MFD (2,1,14) Convolutional Code

The performance curve of the Turbo code has two remarkable features: 1) for very low SNRs the curve is very steep, thus enabling near capacity performance at a BER of 10^{-5} ; and 2) for moderate and high SNRs the curve becomes dramatically less steep resulting in what has been called an “error floor”.

A comparison of the simulation results of the Turbo code with the free-distance asymptote, d , shows that the error floor is simply the result of the code’s approaching the asymptote. See figure 9.

Plotting the contribution to the BER of each spectral line shows that for SNRs less than $E_b/N_0 = 2.5$ dB the performance is not dominated by the free-distance asymptote. Instead, the higher distance paths dominate the performance for these SNRs because of their very large multiplicities; thus, the difference between the real coding gain and the asymptotic coding gain of the (2,1,14) code is due to its very dense distance spectrum.

Figure 9. Decomposed Performance of the MFD (2,1,14) Code

4. PERFORMANCE INTERPRETATION

The following paragraphs attempt to explain some of the factors affecting the performance of the two codes, and the similarities and differences.

The (2,1,14) Code

The performance of the MFD (2,1,14) code is limited by its free-distance asymptote. In addition, for low and moderate SNRs there is a significant gap between the asymptote and the actual performance of the code. This gap can be explained by examining the distance spectrum of the (2,1,14) code.

The distance spectrum of this code is

d	N_d	W_d
18	33	187
20	136	1034
22	835	7857
24	4787	53994
26	27941	361762
28	162513	2374453
30	945579	15452996
32	5523544	99659236

where d is the free distance, N_d is the multiplicity, and W_d is the information weight of all codewords of weight d .

Turbo Codes

The Turbo encoder with a pseudorandom interleaver results in a code with a relatively small free distance but a very low multiplicity. The combination of long block lengths, N , and low multiplicity results in a very small effective multiplicity, N_{eff} , compared to convolutional codes where $N_{\text{eff}} > 1$.

The reduced effective multiplicity results in performance that is superior to codes with much larger free distances at small SNRs. The error floor can be reduced without changing the free distance by increasing the size of the interleaver.

Figure 10 shows the decomposed performance of the code for the different d values and an interleaver length of 100,000, which results in the following distance spectrum:

d	N_d	B_d
6	8	16
8	22	54
10	41	157
12	150	323
14	721	1462

Figure 10. Decomposed Performance of the Turbo Code

In this case, we see that the free-distance term remains the dominant performance parameter even for low SNRs.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The outstanding performance of Turbo codes may be explained in terms of the distance spectrum of the code. The error floor observed in simulations of Turbo codes is a manifestation of the free-distance asymptote. Since Turbo codes have relatively low free distances, the asymptote may be prominent at moderate error rates; however, the error floor can be penetrated by using an outer code such as the R-S code.

The error floor may be lowered by simply increasing the size of the interleaver, but after a certain size a point of diminishing returns is reached (from 10,000 to 64,000 there is a gain of 0.2 dB).

The exceptional performance of Turbo codes at low SNRs is due to spectral thinning and the consequent ability of the code to follow the free-distance asymptote for moderate and low SNRs. For a fixed interleaver size, the performance can be improved by using Maximum Shift Length (MSL) feedback polynomials. This increases the free distance of the overall code and results in better performance at moderate to high SNRs. See Figure 11.

The performance can also be improved by increasing the number of iterations at the decoder, but just as in the case of the length of the interleaver, there is a point of diminishing returns.

Figure 11. Performance of Two Turbo Codes with Different Feedback Polynomials

The next step will be to conduct a real-time test through a space link. We still need answers to the following questions:

- What is the precise effect of the interleaver?
- What is the free distance?
- What is the cause of the performance floor and can it be overcome?
- Can Turbo codes be generalized?
- Can other schemes be found that offer nearly the same performance as Turbo codes with much less decoding complexity?
- What are the effects on the receiver subsystem when operating at -3 dB (such as time to acquire receiver lock and bit synchronization)?

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